

Protocol: SPIRIT-AI extension

Hackathon to test the efficiency and value of ai-powered search systems Yewno and Iris.ai for users and staff at the Royal Library, Denmark

Abstract

This project protocol proposes a hackathon to bring junior researchers, students and library staff together to collaborate on the test of two AI-powered search systems. The participants will work rapidly over a period of 6,5 hours to design research questions and search strategies, conduct searches in test systems and screen and describe related literature. The results will be sent for expert peer review to determine the quality of the results. Pre and post interviews with the participants will contribute to assessments of the value AI-powered search adds to the academic search process.

Introduction

Background

The overall aim of this project is to investigate the extent different artificial intelligence (AI) powered search software support researchers and students in academic literature search. Our findings will inform future services at the university libraries affiliated to the Royal Library in Denmark.

Support through searching using AI-powered technologies can be provided in a multitude of ways – through saving time, through searching more efficiently and effectively, through providing new avenues of discovery and through transparency and documentation. We have a working hypothesis in the project that different types of user (student, senior researchers and library staff) place different values on different types of support. In the first delivery project we stated how AI-powered search is actually defined within the confines of the project, and which AI software will be tested and why, (Wildgaard, Johnsen, & Kiersgaard, 2020: 10.5281/zenodo.4279009). The chosen software has been tested throughout the Spring/Summer of 2021 in Think-Aloud tests with library professionals as test-participants. The aim, to investigate the AI-systems from a search professional point of view. The results of the Think-Aloud tests are yet to be published. The Hackathon however will invite library users to focus on the functionality, efficiency and relevance of two AI-powered search systems for academic searches, where transparency, reproducibility, documentation and reliability are key. The Hackathon event will challenge

users to be creative in their searches and apply their analytical skills and at the same time deliver insights in to their needs for AI-enhanced support at the library.

The two AI-powered search systems that will be tested in the Hackathon are:

Iris.ai: <https://iris.ai/>

Iris.ai navigates Open Access literature, primarily in the disciplines of health and chemistry, but also in other sources that can be tailored to fit the users' needs. Topic modelling and "finger printing" technology is used to display results to the user in topic maps, which the user can then filter their way through to increase specificity. Iris.ai offers free and paid versions of the product, that allow to varying degrees, according to negotiation with the vendor, integration with organisational and subscription databases, collaboration and multi-user functionalities, relevance filters, bookmarking, the possibility to establish inclusion and exclusion criteria to the search, import functions and RSS feeds. Iris.ai can be integrated with reference managers.

Yewno: <https://www.yewno.com/>

Yewno is a multidisciplinary tool that enables the user to search using ideas and concepts rather than keywords. It is designed as a way to develop questions in research projects and get the user to think about the vocabulary they use to frame their work. Technically, this means that fulltext analysis is conducted through the use of computational semantics, neural networks, & Machine-Learning. In a graphic display of results in a concept map, important nodes of concepts are differentiated from ideas related to the concept. The maps are presented in defined contexts, and change according to the context the user finds most useful. Access to the literature is gained by clicking on the nodes on the map. Yewno can be integrated with the library's other discovery services, and can search in academic or government documents published in English, German or Chinese.

Both Iris.ai and Yewno fulfill the requirements to systems supporting academic searches, outlined in (Wildgaard, Johnsen, & Kiersgaard, 2020: 10.5281/zenodo.4279009).

Requirement	Iris.ai	Yewno
use one or more of the building blocks of AI-powered search	Yes	Yes
be designed to support academic literature search	Yes	Yes
be designed to support discovery of related literature/concepts	Yes	Yes
be available for testing over a 2-3 year period	Yes	Yes
be suitable for application in full text resources, databases of references and abstracts in the health science disciplines	Yes	Yes
have clear policies and permissions regarding data collection behaviours and privacy practices	Yes	Yes

support the responsible conduct of research, such as providing functionalities supporting methodological transparency, reproducibility and good citation practice, including documentation of the applied search and ranking/clustering algorithms.	Yes	Yes
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Objectives

The objectives of the project are listed below. These are tangible items that define the [complete project](#).

- Identify AI-powered search systems that supports efficient and relevant outcomes for academic searchers
- Identify AI-powered search systems that improve discovery in our own collections
- Identify AI-powered search systems that supplement the current service portfolio at the Royal Library, Denmark
- Ensure the usefulness of the AI-powered search system for diverse usergroups (information specialists, students, ph.d., researchers and other disciplines)
- Argue for the placement of the AI-powered search system in the KB infrastructure - Biblioteksservice & Partnere (KUB, Rub, AUL) [*Library Service and Partnerships, Copenhagen University Library, Roskilde University Library and Aarhus University Library*], Afdelingen for Bibliotekssystem [*The Department of Library Systems*], Afdeling for Licensforvaltning [*Department of License Negotiation*] og KB Digital [*Department of Digitalisation at the Royal Library, Denmark*].
- Present for library managers what a resulting AI-search service at the library could look like

Specific hypotheses for Hackathon:

- Are the AI-powered search systems Iris.ai and Yewno more efficient than traditional search resources, PubMed, Web of Science and Google Scholar?
- Which value does Iris.ai and Yewno add to the academic search process for users?
- Which value does Iris.ai and Yewno add to the academic search process for information professionals?

Methods

Trial design:

The test set-up is a Hackathon (Schoeb et al, 2020; Wu et al, 2018). Participants are divided into four groups working on the same problem statement and are required to develop their own research question and consequently design their own search in the system they are assigned to.

Prior to the Hackathon all participants are invited to an introductory webinar in each of the ai-powered search systems. Supplementary learning material will also be provided.

On the day of the Hackathon the participants are introduced to the project and the main objectives. They are invited to complete a short introductory survey where we enquire into their knowledge and skills in information seeking, their knowledge/experience in the test systems, and other demographic information (institutional affiliation, status as student, researcher or information specialist). The participants are divided into predefined groups to ensure compatibility within the groups and homogeneity across the groups. Three groups consist of junior researchers, master students and information specialists and represent a research team construction. The fourth group is made up of information specialists alone. The three research team groups are working with either Iris.ai, Yewno or a set of traditional resources (PubMed, Google Scholar and Web of Science). The information specialist group are working with both ai-systems (Iris.ai and Yewno). The Hackathon takes 6,5 hours on one day where all four groups are working independently but in the same room. Throughout the day 3 project members will be observing interaction within the group. A fourth project member will be facilitating the day, providing technical and practical support and importantly refreshments. After the Hackathon, a debriefing survey will be sent to the participants to enquire further into their search experience and considerations.

Problem statement and definition of research task issued to all participants

To be formulated in Appendix 1. Broad topic is "Covid 19"

Tasks for participants in the hackathon

- Complete a pre-interview (short survey)
- Understand the problem statement
- Defining research question(s)
- Search in the systems
- Screen and map the retrieved documents
- Complete a debriefing interview (short survey)
- Write a short (anonymised) one-page summary of the relevant chosen papers for expert review using the template below (Max 20):

<u>Research type facet</u>	<u>Contribution type facet</u>	<u>Paper title</u>	<u>Paper conclusions</u>	<u>Paper ID / URL</u>
<i>What aspect of research are papers about?</i>	<i>What specific element do papers relate to?</i>	<i>Please provide the full paper title</i>	<i>Please provide the paper's key conclusion</i>	<i>Please provide a unique paper ID or URL</i>
Select below one of: validation research, evaluation research, solution proposal, philosophical paper, opinion paper, experience paper, other.	Select below one of: related to a methodology, related to a metric, related to a prototype, related to a process/model, related to a theory, related to an intervention, other.	Insert full title below.	Insert your take on the paper's key take-aways below.	Insert unique ID below.

Tasks for information specialists in the four groups

- One information specialist will be chosen to be a facilitator in each group
- They must take screenshots and ensure documentation for all steps and information flow throughout the tests of the system
- Note the amount of time spent on each search
- Ensure no more than 10 potentially useful papers per groups are selected
- Login to the system with a KB/AU/KU e-mail (Group 1 and 4)
- Log in to the system with VPN
- Login to PubMed NCBI profile, Web of Science, Google Scholar to save the search history and search details (Group 4)

Role of the project group during the Hackathon

- 3 project group members observe the participants (fly on the wall approach. They may not interact with the participants. Observation points are:
 - questions the participants raise with each other and the facilitator,
 - frustrations, thoughts, understanding and interactions with the system

- 1 project group member is the main facilitator/practical person at the Hackathon
 - Respond to questions from the participants that can not be answered within the group
 - Solve technical issues and undertake practical tasks that occur during the day
 - Ensure food, snacks, water and coffee are provided throughout the day

Post Hackathon tasks

- The anonymised results from the hackathon will be sent in peer-review to an expert group who rank search results according to the following:
 - How well did the group manage to explore the overview of the problem? Are there essential parts that are missing? Are there essential parts that they got wrong? Do they cover all main approaches? Do they address all the main challenges? (Max score 10)
 - Are there interesting findings in the results? If yes what is the quality of the findings – are they well described, are they well supported by research, etc (Max score 10)
 - Is the conclusion following the latest trends in research? Is it well supported by research? Does suggest further research activities? To what extend the proposed future activities follow the trends and are well-motivated? (Max score 10)
 - Number of related papers to the field (min. 10 required, max. 20) (Max score 10)
 - Number of “spot on” papers (Max score 10)
 - Number of identified quality papers (Max score 10)
 - Quality is identified as peer-reviewed, strong methodological and/or theoretical framework, good citation practice, well-written, published in a reputable source.

- Debriefing survey covering the following:
 - The purpose of the system they have searched in
 - Rate satisfaction with the system (scale 1-5)
 - The efficiency of the search in the system (scale 1-5)
 - Which aspects of the search system is most useful
 - What the respondents think of a particular functionality in the system
 - The aspects they found most useful, frustrating or confusing
 - Level of documentation in the system
 - Level of transparency in the system

- Communication from or functionalities in the system they feel are missing
- The value they consider the system to have
- Likelihood to use the system again

The project group will make a summary of the results, facilitator documentation, expert review and debriefing surveys:

- A written summary of the search approach for each group, including number of papers found, percentage of relevant papers, percentage spot on papers, time spent on the search, number of maps created and number of search queries
- Overview of the expert review
- User experience

System versions and access

Iris.ai

- E-mail domain recognition at the Royal Library/Aarhus University/Copenhagen University

Yewno

- IP-address recognition (and VPN) for the Royal Library

PubMed

- Login via the Royal Library, KU or AU to allow seamless access to fulltext materials in the library catalogue

Web of Science

- Login via the Royal Library, KU or AU to allow seamless access to fulltext materials in the library catalogue and databases in the Web of Science platform

Google Scholar

- Login with Google-account, and in settings, ensure linking to the Royal Library is activated.

Hackathon practical set-up

- Location: Aarhus
- Date: 8th of November 2021
- One large room with wi-fi and good accoustics
- Two computers per group
- Material for brainstorming (3-4 flip overs, paper, pens, post-it etc.)
- How to access the system for the tests as the users will not have the e-mail or IP address necessary:
 - Computers: use of the 2 information specialist's computer in each group

Participants:

10 Information specialists from the Royal Library, Denmark.

12 Users (Ph.d., KA and researchers)

Minimum 3 experts on the review panel

4 groups for the Hackathon

- Group 1: IRIS.ai
 - 2x information specialist + 4 x users
- Group 2: Yewno
 - 2x information specialist + 4 x users
- Group 3: PubMed/Google Scholar/Web of Science
 - 2x information specialist + 4 x users
- Group 4: Yewno and IRIS.ai

- 4 information specialists

1 expert group for peer review and quality control (after the Hackathon)

- Minimum 3 persons (an uneven number prefers as we may wish to calculate mean values)

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Expert group
Iris.ai	Yewno	PubMed/Google Scholar/Web of Science	Yewno and Iris.ai	Review and quality control
2 information specialists	2 information specialists	2 information specialists	4 information specialists	3 experts
4 other researchers/students	4 other researchers/students	4 other researchers/students		

Participants criteria for inclusion/exclusion:

- User:
 - Master, PhD and post-doc's students only - BA students do not have a routine in academic searching and a minimum of domain knowledge
- Information specialist:
 - Routined search specialists in medical and health literature
 - Routine in PubMed, Web of Science
 - Can search Google Scholar systematically
- Expert:
 - Experts with backgrounds related to the posed scientific question

Group demographics (reporting baseline data):

Number of group members

Group composition

Interventions

Input data

Search terms and search string/strategies formulated from own research question

Output of the AI interventions

Yewno

- Journey
- Concepts
- Definitions
- Maps
- Export/Format: CSV and RIS

Iris.ai

- Knowledge map
- Topics
- Concepts
- Stage 1-3
- Export/Format: CSV and RIS

Pubmed

- Search history
- Search details (search strings, number of articles and time)
- Export
- Format: 'send to citation manager'

Web of Science

- Search history
- Search details (search strings, number of articles and time)
- Export/Format: 'Endnote desktop' - author, title, source, abstract

Google Scholar

- Search history/'my collection'
- Save every search string (otherwise it will delete the strings)
- Export – 10 references per time/Format: Endnote

Outcomes

Primary endpoint:

- Identify the value [Alai](#)-powered search systems have for users and information specialists in academic searches

Secondary endpoints.

- Inform and inspire future services and strategic focus areas at the Royal Library/University Library.
- Disseminate knowledge and insights on [Alai](#)-powered search to colleagues and users at the library.

Sample size

Taken from the surrounding literature on Hackathons in an academic search setting (Schoeb et al, 2020; Wu et al, 2018)

Results

Recruitment

July 2021 - ultimo september 2021

Analyses

Inferential statistical analysis is not part of this study. Descriptive statistics will be conducted using Excel. Qualitative analyses will be undertaken manually in Word, Excel and Nvivo (version 12.0) using Framework matrices.

Qualitative

- Pre-interviews (selected questions)
- Observations and “field notes”
- Debriefing questions (after the Hackathon)

Quantitative

- Pre-interviews (selected questions)
- Relevant papers
- Time spent
- Documentation (screendumps, search history, referencelists, result lists)

- Reproducibility (search strings)

Harms

No harm, adverse effects or ethical concerns

Conflicts of interest

No conflicts of interest have been reported

Limitations

- The comparability of the test groups is dependent on the voluntary participation of the user group
- The testpersons individual of the research topic can bias the groups
- The testpersons individual skills in searching can bias the groups
- Expertise in Iris.ai and Yewno can bias the group
- The two systems are not directly comparable. Both Iris and Yewno Iris.ai are aimed at researchers in the early phase of their project. Whereas Iris.ai combines process tools to map out an overall landscape and build a reading list, Yewno is designed to develop questions in research projects and get the user to think about the vocabulary they use to frame their work.
- The stability of Iris.ai and Yewno can cause unexpected consequences
- Technical problems can bias the set-up

Generalisability of the findings

The findings are limited to the context of the library and local university department/center

The findings are limited to the search topic and available literature on that topic

Generalisability can be improved by comparing our findings to other studies

Registration

It is not necessary to register the protocol for ethical approval. After local peer review, the protocol will be published on Zenodo

Funding

This project is funded by the Royal Library, Denmark

References

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Wu, R., Stauber, V., Botev, V. Elosua, J., Marinov, K., Brede, A., Ritola, M. & Marinov, K. 2018. Scithon™ An evaluation framework for assessing research productivity tools. In WOSP 2018, Miyazaki, Japan. Hakupäivä 1.9.2020. Wu et al, R., Stauber, V., Botev, V., Elosua, J., Marinov, K., Brede, A., & Ritola, M. Scithon™. http://lrec-conf.org/workshops/lrec2018/W24/pdf/7_W24.pdf

Appendix 1: Problem statement and definition of research task issued to all participants. (to be completed)

Short background & problem statement

(i)objective

(ii)objective

(iii)object

Research questions:

1. How can

2. What are

3. Which

4. Can you come up with....

